

AI-driven dog training: Exploring solutions for personalized recommendations

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Abstract—While technology has advanced dog training, many existing solutions remain expensive and focus mainly on the dog, without taking into account the influence of the owner. This research presents a hybrid recommendation system that combines classical machine learning and generative AI to provide personalized training based on both the dog’s and the owner’s characteristics. Taking into account the dynamics of the human-dog relationship, the system offers a more holistic and accessible alternative to current tools. A comparative assessment of both approaches, supported by user feedback, demonstrates their effectiveness and usability. The study provides a dual-model framework that enhances personalization and interactivity in dog training, highlighting the potential of technology to improve the human-dog bond.

I. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between dog and owner is based on mutual trust, understanding and communication, aspects that are strengthened by targeted training and joint activities. Effective dog training not only contributes to the development of the animal’s behavior, but also promotes the emotional bond between humans and pets. However, traditional training methods often rely on personal training or professional trainers, which is expensive and time consuming for many dog owners.

Advances in artificial intelligence and mobile technologies are opening up new opportunities for personalized, digital training solutions. Many existing pet tech applications focus exclusively on the dog and ignore the influence of the owner - such as his experience, lifestyle and interaction behavior - to a large extent. This research addresses precisely this gap by presenting a dual recommendation system that combines classic machine learning techniques with generative AI. The goal is to provide tailored training recommendations that take into account both the characteristics of the dog and the owner.

The focus of this research is on the development and evaluation of a dual system, which comprises two independent approaches: one based on classical machine learning models and one based on generative artificial intelligence. The machine learning models were trained, implemented and optimized on the basis of a specially created data set. The performance of both recommendation systems was evaluated not only by established metrics, but also by user feedback within a web application. This allowed a practical comparison to be made in terms of effectiveness, personalization and user satisfaction.

The original contribution of this work lies in the development and implementation of a dual AI-based recommendation system that explicitly models both dog and owner profiles to generate personalized training and activity suggestions. Unlike existing solutions that focus solely on the dog, this research introduces a novel combination of classical machine learning (trained on a custom-built dataset) and generative large language models, in order to explore their respective strengths and trade-offs in a real-world context. What sets this work apart is the side-by-side integration and evaluation of both AI approaches within an interactive web application, enabling a direct comparison through user testing. This hybrid and comparative framework offers new insights into how AI systems can be tailored not only for animal behavior but also for the dynamics of the human-dog relationship, thus expanding the scope of personalization in pet tech.

II. RELATED WORK

In the field of digital dog training solutions, there already exist several approaches that offer structured recommendations to dog owners. However, what they have in common is that the focus is exclusively on the dog, while individual factors of the owner such as time availability, activity level or patience are often not taken into account, although these contribute significantly to the training dynamics. During the research for the development of this project, the following applications were found:

Woofz — an app with training plans, demo videos and additional features such as a health and walking tracker. It is based on information about the dog and the available training times of the owner. A great advantage is the collaboration with professional dog trainers, which ensures high-quality content. According to experts, “Developed by experts, Woofz offers a comprehensive approach to dog training, providing access to a vast library of tutorials and courses tailored for dogs of all ages and skill levels” [1].

Wiglo — offers personalized recommendations based on a detailed questionnaire. Both the dog’s behaviour and aspects of the human-dog relationship are taken into account. The app is considered to be very precise, but it is paid for, which is could represent a hurdle for many users. “Wiglo is a gamified dog parenting app designed to simplify and enhance the experience of caring for your dog. It allows users to manage daily care, training, health tracking, and reminders all in one place” [2].

YesChat AI — a general AI platform that integrates multiple language models. It allows users to make freely formulated requests for dog training, the advantage being flexibility and free use. However, there is a lack of professional control of the content, which can affect its accuracy.

III. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Many models of artificial intelligence can be used as part of recommendation systems. There are different approaches to the problem and different methods of finding the best one for a particular profile, but this section focuses on how the following models — K-Nearest Neighbors, Naïve Bayes and Logistic Regression — function and how they follow a content-based recommendation approach. These three models were selected for their balance of simplicity, effectiveness, and suitability for personalized recommendations. KNN is flexible and well-suited for real-time, local pattern recognition; Naïve Bayes offers fast and reliable classification even with limited data; and Logistic Regression provides clear probabilistic outputs for binary decisions, making them strong fits for the needs of this project.

A. K-Nearest Neighbors

The k-Nearest-Neighbors (kNN) algorithm is a supervised learning approach that convinces by its simplicity and effectiveness. It only stores the data during training and performs all calculations at the prediction time, which is why it is also considered a lazy learning algorithm. Predictions are made based on the k most similar neighbors of a new data point, with similarity usually calculated over the Euclidean distance:

$$d(x^a, x^b) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m (x_j^a - x_j^b)^2} \quad (1)$$

The similarity search is done locally, which means that no global target function has to be approximated — a property that makes kNN particularly adaptable and efficient.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the algorithm for classifying the next neighbor in two dimensions [1]

kNN is used in many fields, including computer vision, biometric applications and above all referral systems. It is particularly suitable there because of its ability to make personalized suggestions by identifying users or objects with similar characteristics. According to [2], kNN is one of the

most effective methods in recommendation systems because it is easy to implement, has low computational requirements and can still provide relevant, tailored recommendations.

B. Naïve Bayes

Naive Bayes is a simple but efficient linear classifier based on the Bayesian theorem. Despite the unrealistic assumption of the non-dependence on characteristics (“naive”), the algorithm often provides robust results, especially for small samples. It is widely used in areas such as medical diagnosis, RNA analysis or spam filtering, and is characterized by fast calculations, easy implementation and good performance. However, the results for highly dependent features or non-linear problems are often inaccurate. The Naive Bayes classifier is based on the Bayesian rule:

$$\text{Posterior Probability} = \frac{\text{Likelihood} \times \text{Prior Probability}}{\text{Evidence}} \quad (2)$$

In the classification context, it estimates the probability that an object belongs to class i based on the observed attributes.

Fig. 2. Linear (A) vs non-linear problems (B). Random samples for two different classes are shown as colored balls, and the dotted lines indicate the class boundaries that the classes want to approximate by calculating the decision limits. A nonlinear problem (B) would be a case in which linear classes such as naive Bayes are not suitable because the classes are not linearly separable. In such a scenario, nonlinear classes (e.g., instance-based nearest neighbor classes) should be preferred. [3]

Although Naive Bayes is less commonly used in recommendation systems, in [4], the authors propose a hybrid system called RecNBCF that combines Naive Bayes with item-based collaborative filtering (CF). The idea: If CF predictions are weak or unavailable (e.g., cold start), Naive Bayes uses probabilistic predictions. The decision is based on confidence in posterior probabilities.

The recommendation is based on item features (e.g., genre, actors) and normalized user ratings using adjusted cosine similarity. In experiments with MovieLens and FilmTrust datasets, RecNBCF showed better results in accuracy and coverage according to MAE and ROC analyses than six comparison algorithms, including classical CF and pure naive Bayes models.

C. Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a machine learning algorithm used for binary classification tasks. In contrast to linear regression, which predicts continuous values, logistic regression predicts the probability that an instance belongs to a particular class (usually class 1 as a positive class). The model is based on

the logistic function (sigmoid function), which outputs values between 0 and 1.

$$\sigma(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}} \quad (3)$$

where z is a linear combination of the input features [5]. The decision rule is that an instance is classified as positive if the value of the sigmoid function is 0.5, otherwise it is negative.

The relationship between result and predictor variables is represented by the log odds [6]:

$$\text{Log odds} = a + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots + b_nx_n \quad (4)$$

- a = constant term (intercept)
- b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n = regression coefficients (weights) for each predictor variable
- x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n = predictor variables (independent variables)

Although logistic regression is less commonly used in recommendation systems, it provides an interpretable and efficient way to predict user preferences based on article characteristics. In [7] it was shown that this model generates personalized recommendations with Amazon data, which can exceed the base models and mitigate the cold-start problem.

D. Generative AI in recommendation systems

In recent years, generative artificial intelligence has established itself as one of the most groundbreaking technologies in the field of data processing. Unlike traditional AI systems, which are primarily based on analysis and classification, generative AI models generate completely new content such as texts, images or audio using learned patterns from extensive data sets. This ability opens up a wide range of applications, from creative content creation to customer service and software development. Despite its ongoing development process, generative AI already has a significant influence on how we work and communicate today [8].

Generative AI is becoming increasingly important in the field of recommendation systems. Creating new content based on complex patterns can make recommendations more personalized and precise. Generative models allow not only to work on the basis of user-item interactions, but also to integrate multimodal data such as texts, images and videos [9]. Particularly large language models (LLMs) such as GPT-based systems improve the user experience through natural language interaction and differentiated text generation.

The platform chosen for the project is Cohere, a leading natural language processing (NLP) and LLMs offering advanced models for text generation, summary and conversational AI since 2019. Cohere enables easy integration via APIs and supports various cloud providers as well as on-premises installations to realize flexible and secure AI applications.

Studies such as [10] show the versatility of cohere models, for example in the automatic alignment of parallel sentence pairs for languages with few resources. The resulting improved translation data underlines the performance of the Cohere models in real applications.

E. Comparison of traditional and generative AI approaches in recommendation systems

Traditional approaches such as collaborative and content-based filtering work with structured data and predetermined patterns. They are efficient, easy to interpret and proven, but have problems with cold starts and limited context understanding.

Generative AI models, especially large language models such as Cohere, analyze unstructured data such as texts and capture semantic relationships. As a result, they provide personalized and more flexible recommendations, even with little interaction data. In addition, they enable explainable recommendations, but are more computationally intensive and often less transparent.

In summary, traditional methods offer stability and efficiency, while generative AI offers deeper context processing and flexibility. Both approaches have advantages and disadvantages, which will be examined in practice in the following section.

IV. DATASET AND FEATURE ENGINEERING

In order to train the k-Nearest Neighbors, Naive Bayes and Logistic Regression models for the recommendation system, a custom database was created because no existing data set exactly met the requirements. The web application aims to generate personalized recommendations for dog owners, taking into account both the needs of the dog and the characteristics of the owner.

The dataset is based on high-quality domain-specific information from the American Kennel Club [11], which contains detailed descriptions of dog breeds and their typical activity preferences. Inspired by scientific approaches to create custom data sets, a realistic, diverse set of data was generated that maps the different characteristics of owners and dogs.

Fig. 3. Examples of training procedures for generative AI models: (a) generative adversarial networks (GAN), (b) reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) [8]

Fig. 4. View of the database

Using the Python library Pandas, the data was structured and prepared in the form of CSV files for various tables (e.g., owners, dogs, training recommendations, activity recommendations) and inserted into the database. The owners were generated using Python, with attributes such as age and activity level randomly assigned. Each owner was then matched with a dog profile, and personalized, sentence-like recommendation texts were carefully crafted for each pair based on their combined profiles, following the guidelines of the AKC. These recommendations contain individual training and activity tips tailored to the specific characteristics of the dog and owner.

The original database initially contained 300 data sets, which proved to be too small and not variable enough to train the models satisfactorily. Therefore, the data set was gradually expanded to 50,000 entries in order to ensure better generalization and higher accuracy of the models. This extensive data base now forms the basis for training and subsequent evaluation of the used AI models.

V. MODEL TRAINING AND EVALUATION

In the presented system, two separate but parallel working recommendation models were developed: one for training recommendations and one for activity recommendations. Both models simultaneously process the same input data and provide individual suggestions in their specific area. The results are presented together to the user, in order to ensure a comprehensive and coordinated recommendation for each dog-owner pair.

A. K-Nearest Neighbors

For the implementation of the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) model, data was extracted from several SQL tables via a

Metric	Value
Training Recommendation Accuracy	0.5167
Activity Recommendation Accuracy	0.5158
Training Recommendation Precision	0.6541
Training Recommendation Recall	0.5167
Training Recommendation F1-Score	0.5006
Activity Recommendation Precision	0.6530
Activity Recommendation Recall	0.5158
Activity Recommendation F1-Score	0.5003

TABLE I

PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR THE KNN MODELS FOR DOG TRAINING AND ACTIVITY RECOMMENDATIONS BEFORE OPTIMIZATION

Metric	Value
Training Recommendation Accuracy	0.5715
Activity Recommendation Accuracy	0.5723
Training Recommendation Precision	0.6924
Training Recommendation Recall	0.5715
Training Recommendation F1-Score	0.5593
Activity Recommendation Precision	0.6896
Activity Recommendation Recall	0.5723
Activity Recommendation F1-Score	0.5604

TABLE II

PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR THE KNN MODELS FOR DOG TRAINING AND ACTIVITY RECOMMENDATIONS AFTER OPTIMIZATION

pyodbc connection and processed to predict two types of text recommendations - training and activity recommendations - in the context of the implementation.

Data preparation was done using SimpleImputer to handle missing values and LabelEncoder to convert categorical data. The data was then standardized to allow precise distance calculations in the KNN model.

An initial model evaluation without optimization (Table I) showed moderate accuracy, but low recall and F1 values. To improve performance, GridSearchCV was used to determine the optimal value for the k-parameter and applied a 3-fold cross validation (StratifiedKFold). As a result, two optimized KNN models were trained separately for both recommendation types.

In addition, a prediction pipeline has been developed that enables real-time recommendations for new user data. The optimized models showed significant performance improvements in the second table, especially for accuracy, recall and F1-score. Table II

B. Naive Bayes

At the beginning of the project, a recommendation system based on Gaussian Naive Bayes was implemented to predict training and activity recommendations. For this purpose, categorical input data was encoded numerically via one-hot encoding, while the target variables were processed with label encoding.

The first model evaluation was performed without optimization (Table III) and showed moderate performance: the accuracy was about 0.47, while the F1 scores indicated potential for improvement. In order to address this, advanced metrics such as precision, recall and F1 score were used, since accuracy alone does not provide a reliable picture of unbalanced data.

In addition, continuous characteristics such as age have been standardised to analyse their influence - a measure that ac-

Metric	Value
Training Recommendation Accuracy	0.4752
Activity Recommendation Accuracy	0.4621
Training Recommendation Precision	0.4783
Training Recommendation Recall	0.4725
Training Recommendation F1-Score	0.4753
Activity Recommendation Precision	0.4852
Activity Recommendation Recall	0.4710
Activity Recommendation F1-Score	0.4781

TABLE III

PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR THE NAIVE BAYES MODELS FOR DOG TRAINING AND ACTIVITY RECOMMENDATIONS BEFORE OPTIMIZATION

Metric	Value
Training Recommendation Accuracy	0.6056
Activity Recommendation Accuracy	0.6056
Training Recommendation Precision	0.6975
Training Recommendation Recall	0.6056
Training Recommendation F1-Score	0.6013
Activity Recommendation Precision	0.6975
Activity Recommendation Recall	0.6056
Activity Recommendation F1-Score	0.6013

TABLE IV

PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR THE NAIVE BAYES MODELS FOR DOG TRAINING AND ACTIVITY RECOMMENDATIONS AFTER OPTIMIZATION

According to research results [12] can contribute to performance improvement, especially for mixed data types.

After these improvements (second table), both Naive Bayes models achieved a significantly higher accuracy of 0.6056, coupled with improved F1 scores. The performance values of the training and test data showed a high consistency, which indicates good generalizability and a stable model without over- or under-adaptation. Table IV

C. Logistic Regression

Lastly, for the first version of the recommendation system using logistic regression, the input data was transformed using one-hot encoding, while the target variables were encoded numerically with label encoding.

However, the initial model evaluation (Table V) showed only weak performances with accuracies of around 44%, which indicated optimization potential. To compensate for the class discrepancy, random oversampling was applied to the training data - based on findings from [13]. In addition, the model has been adapted with `class_weight='balanced'` to give the minority class a stronger weight. After these measures, the models improved significantly: accuracy increased to over 54% (Table VI), and F1 values also increased.

Metric	Value
Training Recommendation Accuracy	0.4411
Activity Recommendation Accuracy	0.4324
Training Recommendation Precision	0.4754
Training Recommendation Recall	0.4411
Training Recommendation F1-Score	0.4542
Activity Recommendation Precision	0.4789
Activity Recommendation Recall	0.4324
Activity Recommendation F1-Score	0.4512

TABLE V

PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR THE LOGISTIC REGRESSION MODELS FOR DOG TRAINING AND ACTIVITY RECOMMENDATIONS BEFORE OPTIMIZATION

Metric	Value
Training Recommendation Accuracy	0.5456
Activity Recommendation Accuracy	0.5402
Training Recommendation Precision	0.6610
Training Recommendation Recall	0.5456
Training Recommendation F1-Score	0.5345
Activity Recommendation Precision	0.6602
Activity Recommendation Recall	0.5402
Activity Recommendation F1-Score	0.5287

TABLE VI

PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR THE LOGISTIC REGRESSION MODELS FOR DOG TRAINING AND ACTIVITY RECOMMENDATIONS AFTER OPTIMIZATION

D. Final findings

To further analyze the performance of the trained models, the accuracy values for both the training and test data sets were compared. This comparison helps to identify signs of over- or underfitting. Overfitting occurs when a model performs well in training data but is not generalised to unseen data, while underfitting refers to a model that performs poorly in both training and test data and indicates that it has not learned the underlying patterns. The results are shown in the graphs below: (Figure 5)

Fig. 5. Accuracy comparisons for training and testing performance, in order to identify possible overfitting or underfitting trends for each of the used models; Training Recommendation and Activity Recommendation models, developed using: 1. k-Nearest Neighbors, 2. Naive Bayes, 3. Logistic Regression

Based on this analysis and the previously presented evaluation results from the tables, the most suitable model for the project was selected - exclusively based on the performance indicators and the behavior of the models with regard to overfitting or underfitting.

To select the best model, KNN, Naive Bayes and Logistic Regression were evaluated using typical metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score. Despite low accuracy values - due to the complex, paragraph-based structure of the target variables - all models showed certain strengths. KNN achieved solid values, but suffered from slight overfitting. The logistic regression was inconsistent and showed both over- and underfitting. Naive Bayes, on the other hand, proved to be the most stable model with balanced performance, without strong deviations between training and test results. Due to this robustness and simplicity, Naive Bayes was eventually selected as the final model for the application, on the machine learning side of the dual recommendation system.

VI. GENAI INTEGRATION

The project integrated generative AI into the recommendation system, using Cohere's powerful command-r-plus-03-2025 language model. This model, with 111 billion parameters, was chosen for its efficiency, scalability and high response

quality. It is particularly suitable for business-related applications and was easily integrated into the application via a free trial with API access. This allowed extensive tests to be carried out and the model to be optimally adapted.

A central component of the development was the prompt engineering. Initially, simple prompts were used that relied directly on user-related data such as dog type, activity level or leisure behavior of the owner. However, these often led to poorly structured or inconsistent texts. Therefore, the focus was increasingly on structured, precisely formulated prompts. Initially, attempts were made to unify editions by means of character restrictions, but this often led to incomplete texts. Finally, this limitation has been abandoned in favor of a better coherence of content.

Iterative refinement of the prompts resulted in a format that provides fluid, complete and user-friendly recommendations - without formal formatting such as bold or italics. This approach not only improved the comprehensibility, but also the practical applicability of the generated content and made the generative AI a meaningful part of the final application.

To illustrate this process, here is an example of the initial prompt format used during early testing:

“Given a dog with breed {dog_trait}, size {dog_size}, and age {dog_age}, and an owner with age {owner_age}, activity level {activity_level}, free time {free_time}, and patience level {patience_level}, provide a short dog training recommendation.”

The values in the brackets correspond to specific in-app profile information for the dog and owner, which the AI uses to tailor the recommendations.

After iterative improvements, the final prompt format implemented in the application was refined as follows:

“Provide a short recommendation for dog training. Ensure the recommendation is a complete thought and does not cut off mid-sentence. End at a natural, logical stopping point without abrupt cuts. Do not use bold, italics, or indents. Given a dog with breed {dog_trait}, size {dog_size}, and age {dog_age}, and an owner with age {owner_age}, activity level {activity_level}, free time {free_time}, and patience level {patience_level}, generate the recommendation accordingly.”

Again, the bracketed values represent dynamic profile data from the app, allowing personalized, context-aware suggestions.

This refinement helped improve the fluency and usability of the generated recommendations, making the generative AI component a valuable addition to the overall system.

VII. USER STUDY AND FEEDBACK

A. Web application overview

The project consists of a Python-based web application with two databases: one for data storage and one for training the AI models. For the backend and server-side logic, the Flask framework was used, which convinces by its simplicity, flexibility and scalability. Flask enables the creation of maintainable and controlled web applications without rigid structures.

The front-end used the JavaScript framework Vue.js, which provides a responsive, component-based user interface. Vue supports step-by-step integration and allows the creation of dynamic, user-friendly pages such as login, profile and main page. Animated elements and interactive functions were created using tutorials and sample codes from W3Schools and GeeksforGeeks.

For the database creation and management, Microsoft SQL Server was used, which impresses with high performance, stability and advanced query functions. MSSQL is particularly well suited for managing structured data and supports complex queries that are necessary for the application’s data-driven functions.

The choice of these technologies was based on their compatibility and suitability for a robust, yet manageable project. Flask and Vue.js enable a modular and scalable architecture with good user experience, while MSSQL provides a stable database. In addition, these technologies offer sufficient flexibility for the future integration of various AI models, both generative and proprietary training models. This allows the backend to easily integrate AI functionalities for personalized recommendations, while the frontend responds dynamically and enables seamless user interaction.

The web application is divided into several central routes managed with Flask, covering different user-oriented functions including main page, login, registration, home page, profile and recommendation pages. The login, logout and signup functions are based on user session management best practices in Flask. After successful login, users are taken to the home page, which serves as a central access point to their profile and personalized recommendations.

B. User-based evaluation of the dual recommendation system

To evaluate the practical effectiveness and user perception of the developed recommendation system, a structured test session with 12 participants was conducted. The selected users were dog owners or previous dog owners, aged between 21 and 57 years. Each user was asked to create an account within the application, fill in the profile for themselves and their dog, and then generate personalized recommendations. For each individual configuration, the system created two proposals: one based on the classical AI model and one generated by the generative AI model. It was important that the users did not know which recommendation came from which system. This deliberately neutral presentation of content ensured that the decisions were based solely on the perceived quality and usefulness of the recommendations and not influenced by technological assumptions.

At the bottom of the recommendation page of the application, users could indicate which recommendation they preferred by clicking on the corresponding button with the inscription “I prefer this version”. The selection was then stored in the database in the “Preference” table provided for this purpose, so that a visual evaluation could be made later.

A total of 35 recommendation pairs were generated. Of these, the suggestions of classical AI were selected 22 times,

while in 13 cases generative AI recommendations were preferred. This distribution is illustrated in Figure 6. The graph clearly shows the majority in favor of the traditional method, indicating a stronger preference of users for their content.

Fig. 6. Graphic showing the choices made by users regarding the classical AI model and the GenAI generated recommendations

In the subsequent discussions, many of those who had opted for the traditional AI variant said that they would have appreciated above all the higher level of detail and the stronger focus on the relationship between dog and owner. The proposals were more structured and personal. In contrast, users who preferred the generative AI answers described them as shorter, clearer and easier to understand. They were perceived as helpful, especially when quick and compact recommendations were desired.

In summary, the feedback shows that both AI systems have different strengths and address different user needs. While some users prefer more detailed and contextual recommendations, others prefer concise and quick-to-grasp suggestions. The ability to offer both variants in parallel was seen by the test subjects as a clear strength of the application, as it allowed them to deal with the system in the way that best suited their information style.

VIII. DISCUSSION

In the application, two different AI approaches were compared: a traditional model based on a Naïve Bayes classifier and a generative model based on a large language model. Both methods were integrated into the platform in parallel to provide personalized recommendations for dog training and activities. The aim was to give users the opportunity to experience both systems and express their preferences on this basis.

The traditional AI was characterized by consistency and traceability, as it always delivered the same results with the same inputs. Their recommendations were structured, detailed and often heavily tailored to real, observable patterns. Users found this type of output to be helpful and trustworthy, as it provided concrete and practical guidance. However, weaknesses also appeared in individual cases, when recommendations did not quite fit the profile — for example, in the case of a young dog, for which advice for senior dogs was proposed.

In contrast, generative AI showed a high degree of flexibility. It was also able to produce fluid, coherent texts for

less typical profiles that reliably referred to input details such as dog age, breed or owner activity level. Their answers were usually shorter, more understandable and seemed more modern. Nevertheless, generative AI was sometimes perceived as too general or repetitive and its suggestions were sometimes superficial. In addition, it was not clear how exactly the decision came about in the background, as the model functioned as a "black box".

In a user review test with 12 participants and 35 pairs of recommendations, the quality of the proposals was directly compared without revealing which version came from which system. In 22 cases, users opted for the classical and in 13 cases for the generative variant. Especially the depth, structure and the stronger focus on the relationship between dog and owner were mentioned as reasons for the preference of the traditional model.

In summary, the traditional AI model was the more reliable, understandable and trustworthy option in this application context. It best met users' needs in terms of clarity, depth of detail and profile relevance. Generative AI, on the other hand, complemented the system with linguistic diversity and flexibility and remains a useful extension, especially for creative, less structured tasks.

IX. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, a dual recommendation system that combines classical machine learning with generative artificial intelligence was developed, aiming to provide personalized suggestions for dog training and activities. Unlike conventional systems, this approach considers not only the dog's behavior but also owner-related factors such as age, lifestyle, and character traits, seeking a more holistic perspective.

The system employs two parallel approaches: a traditional AI model offering consistent and interpretable results through structured data analysis, and a generative AI model that produces flexible, context-aware recommendations using natural language processing. Initial evaluation through performance metrics and user feedback suggested a preference for the classic model, primarily due to its structured and detailed recommendations. However, these findings are preliminary and based on a limited user sample.

Future work will focus on expanding the system's coverage to include additional breeds—particularly mixed and rare breeds—and on enhancing the quality and diversity of training data to reduce bias and improve recommendation accuracy. From a technical standpoint, exploring ensemble methods and fine-tuning generative models specifically for dog training may further enhance the system's capabilities.

Overall, this platform represents an early-stage prototype that shows potential as an intelligent, user-centered recommendation system. Continued development and more extensive validation will be necessary to better understand its practical impact and to refine its ability to address the diverse needs of dogs and their owners.

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